

Enhancing Machine Learning Detection Technique to Secure E-mail Communication against Malware-based Phishing Attacks

Eng. Kambey L. Kisambu
Cyber Security Specialist
e-Government Authority &
University of Dodoma, Tanzania
kambeylk@gmail.com

Dr. Mohamedi Mjahidi
Lecturer, Department of Computer
Science,
University of Dodoma, Tanzania
mmjahidi@gmail.com

Dr. Tabu S. Kondo
Lecturer, Department of Computer
Science,
University of Dodoma, Tanzania
chifulukwe@gmail.com

Abstract-Phishing attacks are among the most significant threats to Internet users and are challenging to identify and protect. In the fight against phishing attacks, several approaches including machine learning techniques have been deployed to detect phishing attacks. However, phishers have sophisticated their methods to escape detection by using different techniques for obfuscation. This study evaluated seven classifiers, which are SVM, MNB, MLP, RF, LR, DT, and K-NN to determine the top-performing algorithm for more enhancement to improve phishing attacks detection. The study applied hybrid features selection based on Pearson correlation and URL based features and RF was the leading algorithm with an accuracy of 99.28% thanks to the hybrid technique, which integrated 17 features with higher coefficient ratios and the most popular URL patterns. This imply that the enhanced classifier when integrated with mail filters, it can improve phishing e-mails detection and ultimately secure e-mail communication against malware-based phishing attacks.

Keywords: Malware; malware-based phishing; phishing attacks; classifier, machine learning algorithms; phishing detection techniques.

I. INTRODUCTION

Malicious software, or malware, is one of the biggest dangers that internet users have to deal with. With the rise of smart phones and internet connectivity, malware is becoming a significant problem in today's digital society. Cybercriminals utilize malware, a type of malicious software, to obstruct computer programs, access a system, or gather sensitive data. Malware and botnets, which are frequently used to conduct such assaults, are the major source of computer security problems, including the proliferation of phishing. Among the most significant threats to Internet users are malware-based phishing attempts, which are challenging to identify and protect against since they don't seem malevolent. Phishing is a type of cybercrime when an attacker pretends to be an official entity through e-mails or other forms of electronic communication in order to impersonate a real person or organization [1].

Due to its continuous development, the term “phishing” has been advocated differently on the ground of its operation and context, thus, there is no conventional elaboration for the word phishing [2]. In Phishing attacks, e-mail is the most attack vector and usually the phisher uses some captivating words which necessitate emotional reaction to the person to induce them into opening the related URL link. Customarily, phishers conduct their attacks either by persuading users into revealing their sensitive data (i.e. deceptive attacks) or by using high-tech deception to trick users into disclosing personal information [2]. Despite the fact that phishers prefer illusory attacks to technological solutions, technical technique mitigation cannot be disregarded. Malware-based phishing, which falls under technical trickery, and six (6) sub-attack strategies are the focus of this research. Figure 1 shows types of phishing attacks and approaches utilized by phishers to carry out the attack.

Figure 1: Types of phishing attacks and techniques deployed by phishers.
Source: [2].

More recent studies, including those by Basit et al (2021) and Ozcan et al (2021), revealed that phishing attempts surged during the Corona virus pandemic (COVID-19), and phishers utilize COVID-19 to trick their intended target and users, especially those in healthcare facilities. The reports from various sources such as Internet Crime Report [5] revealed that computer-generated attacks associated with COVID-19 including phishing were generally increased from March 2020. As per RiskIQ (security organization), the COVID-19 pandemic has resulted in a significant increase in various cyber-attacks targeting various businesses all over the world, as cyber criminals have taken advantage of the situation [6]. Furthermore, in Business E-mail Compromise (BEC) attacks, the typical wire transfer request fell by 14% to \$93,881 in Q3 2022, down from \$109,467 in Q2 according to APWG. However, the number of wire transfer BEC attacks in Q3 of 2022 increased by 59% compared to Q2 of 2022. In the 3rd quarter, the attacks against software as a service (SaaS) and mail service remain steady at 17% whereas advance fee fraud scams circulated via e-mail climbed by 1,000% (APWG, 2022).

In Tanzania, the number of internet users increased from 31.2 million to 34.05 million between January 2023 and June 2023, according to TCRA data (TCRA, 2023). These figures demonstrate the widespread usage of the internet and the significant number of internet users who fall prey to phishing scams both domestically and globally. TCRA has established a Computer Emergency Response Team known as TZ-CERT, to response for cyber security events that include phishing and malware attacks.

In general, various studies and researches have been conducted on the subject of phishing attacks, with different approaches and techniques including those that used machine learning. The studies by Meenu & Godara (2019), Gibert et al (2020), Rashid et al (2020), Gori Mohamed & Visumathi (2020), Rameem Zahra et al (2021), Gupta et al (2021), Alkhalil et al (2021) and Madhavan et al (2021) have all of them dealt with detecting and mitigating phishing attacks. Even though some of the studies used machine learning, which are the most innovative methods for discovering phishing attacks, the majority of the studies focused on phishing attacks in general. In addition, most

of the researches were conducted using datasets in English other than few that included Lithunia, Arabic and Chinese languages. Unfortunately, there is insubstantial research conducted using regional languages such as Swahili language, which is extensively used in Eastern Africa countries and other neighboring countries. Consequently, this paper seeks to deeply going through the pertinent researches in the area of malware-based phishing to determine the varieties of studies that have been done before, what were the outcome, the deficiencies and the suggested further work. The study evaluated the performance of machine learning (ML) algorithms using datasets based on English and Swahili language and COVID-19 related datasets.

This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides an overview of some literature reviews including related works; Section 3 describes methodologies; Section 4 explores ML algorithms, experiment made with results and performance evaluation. In section 5, the paper provides the conclusions of the study and future work.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Malware-based Phishing Attacks Phases

A typical phishing attempt with three levels of phishers is shown in Figure 2. As seen in phases 1-3, mailers start by sending out a lot of misleading e-mails (usually using botnets), which guide victims to misleading websites or download malicious programs and install it on their computer. The malicious texts are often hidden from view in the second step by the attackers using obfuscation techniques [13].

Figure 2: Malware-based Phishing Attacks Phases and Stages

2.2 Threats from Malicious E-mails

The landscape of e-mail threats is always changing and Cybercriminals create new strategies every year for tricking and harming their victims via e-mails and other attacking vectors. The key hazards are constant despite differences in context, circumstances, and e-mail kinds. Malware URLs, malicious attachments, and social engineering are the three main e-mail dangers. All of these risks can result in data loss, information theft, business disruption, and financial loss. The majority of phishing e-mails contain at least one of these three threats. Understanding these threats and implementing robust security measures is crucial for protecting against the ever-changing tactics of cybercriminals.

2.2.1 Phishing E-mails with Harmful Attachments

Malicious e-mail attachments have been found to contain malicious software which can launch ransomware attacks, install viruses, Trojan horses, bots, spyware, or infect office files through macros (APT). Malware is designed to run when an e-mail attachment is opened. It can take the form of official-sounding or interesting documents, PDFs, voice-mails, photos, e-faxes, or other types of data. According to a Symantec report released in 2019, 1 in 412 e-mails were found malicious, and 48% of all malicious attachments were word and excel files. Over 65% of data breaches are due to phishing e-mails and hacked business e-mails [14]. E-mail attachments included in phishing e-mails are risky due to the unknown content they may contain. Malware embedded in an attachment can be executed if opened. The suspicious URL can also be inside a PDF document as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Suspicious URL inside PDF document

As per statistic in Figure 4, Microsoft Office files like .xls and .doc and archive files like .zip are the most often utilized attachment types in phishing e-mails, according to Cisco's e-mail threat report from 2019. It can be challenging to discern between trustworthy and malicious attachments since the files are frequently included as e-mail attachments.

Malicious attachment type		Top 10 Malicious extensions in e-mail	
Type	Percentage	Extension	Percentage
Office	42.80%	.doc	41.80%
Archive	31.20%	.zip	26.30%
Script	14.10%	.js	14.00%
PDF	9.90%	.pdf	9.90%
Binary	1.77%	.rar	3.90%
Java	0.22%	.exe	1.70%
Flash	0.0003%	.docx	0.80%
		.ace	0.60%
		.gz	0.50%
		.xlsx	0.49%

Figure 4: Category of malicious attachments used in e-mail

Source: Cisco Cybersecurity, (2019).

2.2.2 Phishing E-mail with Malicious URL

Phishing attacks utilizing malicious URLs are one of the biggest dangers to cybersecurity experts and practitioners. The body of an e-mail or an attachment may contain a clickable link to a malicious URL. Malicious URLs are frequently hidden behind inappropriate language, buttons, or graphics. According to a Symantec analysis of data from 2020, every 170 e-mail URL contained a malicious URL. It is also possible to utilize a website address that directs the target to a fake website. Attackers utilize "obfuscation techniques" to hide malicious URLs that are statistically indistinguishable to benign ones in an effort to prevent static analysis of lexical properties [15].

Figure 5 illustrates how a text link or HTML element might conceal a URL. Although the button says "Go to Apple ID Account," clicking it leads to a bogus Apple website. When someone hover the mouse over the button, the URL appears is not the same as Apple's certified website (<https://www.apple.com>).

Figure 5: Screen-shot of URL in HTML component

2.3 Related Works

As described in various spam classification research studies such as Gibert et al (2020) and Abdul Abiodun et al (2021), the fight against spam and phishing is very challenging since phishers continue to circumvent some existing countermeasures. However, there are numerous approaches and tactics for combating spam and phishing that are continuing to be improved to minimize the damage of attack. E-mail security filters, which use purifying techniques, are one of the most commonly used approaches in combating spammers. The approach is the most effective way to identify malware and spam because both have characteristics that the machine can learn by using data that has already been collected in the machine learning algorithm (SC et al., 2021).

Figure 6 illustrates the key phases in a ML approach to spam and scam mail screening. The technique begins by tokenizing the message body after it has been received in order to extract the words from it. Following tokenization, the next step is to change the words back to their original form (lemmatization, e.g., "extracting" to "extract"). Stop-words are also removed by removing words that appear frequently in many texts (e.g., "the," "you," "and," "to," "a," and "for") [18]. Relative Frequency with Power Transformation (RFPT) is a different spam filtering method that Malero (2014), provided as an alternative to the traditional features known as Term Frequency with Inverse Document Frequency (TFIDF). The approach is combined with the lemmatization technique, and it significantly outperformed TFIDF [19]. Finally, the presentation modifies the messages so that a ML algorithm can classify them.

Figure 6: E-mail filtering Process

Rastenis et al (2021) analyzed current spam and phishing e-mail classification methods and found from several studies that they are all primarily concerned with classifying known and harmful e-mail. A solution based on e-mail header and message body text classification was presented, which categorizes e-mails as phishing or spam. They

explored the suitability of automated dataset translation to adjust it to e-mail classification written in other languages because most public e-mail datasets almost exclusively accumulate English e-mails. The research focuses on e-mail classification solutions written in three languages: English, Lithuanian, and Russian. The study's suggested resolution of automated transformation for dataset augmentation and adaptation for the three languages demonstrates that the classification outcomes do not suffer as a result of the automated translation. The accuracy obtained for English-only text was 90.07% +- 3.17%, while it was 89.2% +- 2.14% for multi-language texts (English, Russian, and Lithuanian). The study did not show how feature optimization affects e-mail classification performance.

Madhavan et al (2021) highlighted the comparative study of identifying fake e-mails using various practical ML analysis and the recommended approaches, while taking into account different evaluation metrics including accuracy, efficiency, error, and model evaluation time. The paper discussed problems based on a number of drawbacks in spam filtering and categorization when a particular method is taken into account, including price, assessment time, and computing resources. The study contrasts the benefits, limitations, and shortcomings of a few existing methods that employ machine learning methodology to recognize spam e-mails (Madhavan et al., 2021). A hybrid algorithm was recommended as the best and most practical approach for spam recognition in e-mail communication to solve the identified problems, even though the study did not demonstrate the created algorithm's peak efficiency. The study only considered spam detection but there was no malware-based phishing detection.

Phomkeona & Okamura (2020) proposed a novel method for extracting e-mail features as well as a deep-learning approach for detecting zero-day malware spam. Several APIs were used to extract features from e-mail header and body parts, such as risk words detected, machine translation discovered, and other features. They also used e-mail datasets from four different languages to build a word database for more variety and a more realistic purpose. The experiment results showed that zero-day e-mail spam detection was 78% accurate and normal spam detection was 92.8% accurate. The accuracy rate for features employed in zero-day e-mail spam detection did not considerably increase because the spam e-mail dataset utilized only contains regular spam and not malicious one. To maximize accuracy and improve phishing detection, the dataset for this study must be balanced to include both malicious and phishing datasets.

Gibert et al (2020) offered a useful overview of perspectives on the discovery and categorization of malware using machine learning. The aim job, input attributes, classification algorithm, dataset characteristics, and various research articles were evaluated and examined. Four significant additions were provided, including literature on malware detection using deep learning and a thorough explanation of the techniques and features in a standard machine learning workflow. The final contribution included research problems and difficulties, with a focus on concept drift and difficulties with adversarial learning, among other things. The study insisted on a constant struggle between security experts and malware developers due to the complexity of malware production as innovation rises (Gibert et al 2020). This study emphasizes the importance of increasing effort in the never-ending fight to mitigate attacks, particularly malware-based phishing outbreaks, in order to secure e-mail message.

III. METHODOLOGY

Figure 7 illustrates the research environment and procedures used in this study, which include a literature review, data collecting and processing, real-world experimentation, and merging the machine learning model with the spam

filter. The specifics of each step are explained in the following subsection based on the category of research question it falls under. The first step begins with a systematic literature review, followed by data collection, which explains how and where data were collected, and then a section on dataset creation is discussed. The entire data processing process including pre-processing, classifier training, and evaluation was carefully reviewed. In order to complete the study, the machine learning model was improved and merged with the spam filter based on the top-performing ML algorithm. An emulation experiment was run on a virtual server with Python packages loaded along with mail server components like Postfix, Dovecot, Amavis, SpamAssassin, and Webmail in order to conduct this research.

Figure 7: Research Steps to be adopted

3.1 Systematic Literature Review

The systematic literature review (SLR) mainly covered various studies, tools such as threat intelligence tool, related works and features for malware-based phishing e-mails attacks to present background for the topic. The characteristics of malware-based phishing assaults have been identified and examined using a SLR. For this investigation, the SLR processes were reported using the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) method. The PRISMA 2020 approach was used as it makes it easier to report clearly on SLR by offering a thorough checklist and flow diagram that direct the reviewing process [22].

Moreover, researching using keywords extracted from the research title and abstract in order to obtain relevant knowledge in the study was considered to narrow the search and obtain relevant literature. The journal articles were searched and downloaded from five reputable scholarly publication search engines namely Google Scholar, Science Direct, ACM Digital Library, Research Gate and IEEE Xplore. Some of the keywords used for searching was "malware", "phishing", "malware-based" and "phishing attacks. In total, 92 journal articles out of 108 were downloaded from more than five search engines in the first five pages, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of Downloaded Articles from Search Engines

Scholarly database & Search Engine	URL	Articles	Percentage (%)
Google Scholar,	https://scholar.google.com/	12	13.04
Science Direct,	https://www.sciencedirect.cm/	18	19.57
Research Gate	https://researchgate.com	24	26.09
ACM Digital Library	https://dl.acm.org/	15	16.30
IEEE Xplore	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org	14	15.22
Other Scholarly	Various URLs	9	9.78
TOTAL ARTICLES		92	100

The findings show that the titles of about 29 journal articles were mismatched with the study objective, resulting in their elimination. Among the 29 journal articles, 6 were removed from Google Scholar, 4 from IEEE Xplore, 7 from Science Direct, 9 from Research Gate, 3 from the ACM Digital Library. After the first exclusion, approximately 63 journal articles remained. After a critical review of the abstract and full text of each of the 63 journal articles, 27 were screened for exclusion. The removal was based on the following factors: full text, in which 4 articles were excluded; duplicates, in which 6 articles were excluded; year of publication from 2006 to 2022, in which 2 articles were removed; non English language articles in which 3 articles removed; and 12 articles were excluded due to disparities in the text's contents compared to the current study's objective. Finally, approximately 36 journal articles remained for further step in determining features used for phishing e-mail detection that is explained in section 4.2.

3.2 Data Collection

This research used two categories of data: (1) primary data, which is data collected directly from the field for the first time (i.e., unprocessed), and (2) secondary data, which is data collected by other researchers, analyzed, and has already gone through the statistical process. All e-mails datasets arrived as individual files and each file is an RFC 822-encoded e-mail message [23]. In total, the datasets were comprising of English Phishing dataset (14,651), COVID-19 related content (3,192) and Swahili Phishing dataset (1,687) as summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Summary for primary datasets

	Swahili Dataset		English Dataset		COVID-19 Dataset		Combined Dataset	
	Phish	Ham	Phish	Ham	Phish	Ham	Phish	Ham
	78	1,609	6,234	8,417	113	3,079	6,424	12,979
Total	1,687		14,651		3,192		19,403	

Since the secondary datasets were string-based text files, the researchers used them to access publically accessible datasets and added each email as a separate text file. In total, the datasets were comprised of 11,056 e-mails datasets that was gathered from Enron dataset, SpamAssasin and Nazario dataset as shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Summary for secondary datasets

	Enron dataset		SpamAssasin Dataset		Nazario Dataset		Combined Dataset	
	Phish	Ham	Phish	Ham	Phish	Ham	Phish	Ham
	108	2,256	982	2,698	1,764	3,248	3,793	7,263
Total	2,364		3,680		5,012		11,056	

3.3 Data Processing and Feature Extraction

In general, e-mail communication contains many stop words, commas, full stops, quotation marks and single quotes, which are incompatible with most tools and necessitate pre-processing of datasets. The importance of pre-processing the dataset and selecting the best classifier have a significant impact on the outcome and dependability of the machine learning-based approach [11]. Data processing stages include feature extraction, standardization, dataset separation, and attribute weighting.

Although appropriate feature selection involves extracting a subset of characteristics, image compression involves linearly combining the novel features and functionality [24]. The key purpose of feature extraction is to generate a

set of words from free text view verdicts without altering the semantic meaning of the words. In total, there were thirty-one (31) features that were extracted and used in this study as retrieved from WEKA and presented in figure 15 based on correlation coefficients ranking.

The e-mail feature extraction was done by conditional logic expression presented by feature 1 to feature 4 as presented from (i) to (iv).

i) Check if the e-mail contains suspicious word

$$\text{Features 1: IF } \begin{cases} \text{Suspicious_e - mail_subject|suspicious_e - mail_greetings} \rightarrow \text{Phishing} \\ \text{Otherwise} \rightarrow \text{Legitimate} \end{cases}$$

ii) Check if attached file has malicious extension such as ".exe" and ".bat".

$$\text{Features 2: IF } \begin{cases} \text{filename.exe|filename.bat} \rightarrow \text{Phishing} \\ \text{Otherwise} \rightarrow \text{Legitimate} \end{cases}$$

iii) GET request of the HTTP protocol to verify the legitimacy of an URL.

$$\text{Features 3: IF } \begin{cases} \text{GET(link}_{url}) \neq \text{link}_{url} \rightarrow \text{Phishing} \\ \text{Otherwise} \rightarrow \text{Legitimate} \end{cases}$$

iv) Check URL shorteners as e-mail is suspicious if it includes a short URL.

$$\text{Features 4: IF } \begin{cases} (\text{Link}_{url} \text{ is short}_{url} \text{ or link}_{url} \text{ is hidden inside image} \\ \text{or clicked text}) \rightarrow \text{Phishing} \\ \text{Otherwise} \rightarrow \text{Legitimate} \end{cases}$$

3.4 Selected Machine Learning Algorithms

In this paper, data extracted from a total of 36 articles in the SLR was revised and scrutinized using a content analysis methodology to conclude the ML classifiers to train and test the correctness of phishing e-mail detection. Content analysis can be defined as a method of analyzing text data and enumerating the results [25]. According to the study by Jidagam & Rizk (2016), a good Data Mining model to forecast classifier performance is estimated to have accuracy score above 80%. As a result, the components of the analysis approaches adopted when deciding on the ML algorithms used in this study were based on the performance of accuracy metrics. Out of the qualified 36 articles, only 24 articles examined were found to evaluate more than one ML technique using accuracy evaluation metric. The classifiers from the articles with the accuracies shown in Table 5 were Support Vector Machine (SVM), Multilayer Perceptron (MLP), Multinomial Naïve Bayes (MNB), Random Forest (RF), Logistic Regression (LR), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Decision Tree (DT), Artificial Neural Network (ANN) and Gaussian Naïve Bayes (GNB). The selection of the right machine learning algorithm depends on several fundamental factors, including performance, processing time, error rates, and specific use cases. Each factor plays a crucial role in ensuring the chosen algorithm achieves a balance between performance, computational efficiency, and robustness to errors and noise, thereby facilitating a comprehensive evaluation in the research.

Table 4: Data Mining Methods in Relation with Accuracy Evaluation Metrics

S/N	REFERENCE	M	D	R	G	K	S	L	A	M
		N	T	F	N	N	V	R	N	P
		B			B	N	M		N	
1	A. E. L. Aassal et al., (2020)	98.38%	99.76%	99.90%	97.95%	97.33%	99.95%	99.95%		
2	Alshira'h & Al-Fawa'reh, (2020)	77%	97%	98%		98%	99%	95%		88%
3	Abdul Abiodun et al., (2021)	69.90%	78.20%	96.10%		72.90%			74.60%	
4	Sachin Barahate et al., (2021)		98%	98%	59%	94%	94%	92%		
5	Rawal et al., (2017)	99.81		99.87		99.87%		99.81		
6	Yasin & Abuhasan, (2016)	95.4		99.1			96.9			97.7
7	Nandhini & Marseline, (2020)	79.5		99.9		99.90%	90.8	93.1		
8	Ojewumi et al., (2022)			98.40%		93.40%	91.70%			
9	Mohamed et al., (2022)			78.90%			85.50%		85.20%	
10	Rayan, (2022)		92%	84%						88%
11	Sethi et al., (2017)		100%	97.70%			99.50%			
12	Tubyte & Paulauskaite-Taraseviciene, (2021)		94%	96.80%			96.60%	92%		

The highest and lowest accuracy for each classifier were observed and the average calculated based on the average mean from the highest and lowest accuracy of each machine learning classifier used in the 12 journal articles analyzed, as shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Average Mean of Highest and Lowest Accuracy Metric

ML ALGORITHM	MNB	DT	RF	ANN	KNN	SVM	LR	GNB	MP
HIGHEST SCORE	99.81	100	99.9	85.2	99.9	99.95	99.95	97.95	97.7
LOWEST SCORE	69.9	78.2	78.9	74.6	72.9	85.5	92	55	88
TOTAL AVERAGE	84.86	89.1	89.4	79.9	86.4	92.73	95.98	76.48	92.85

By taking into account the results in Table 5 and the study by Jidagam & Rizk (2016) that described the recommended accuracy score (80%) for a Data Mining model to forecast classifier performance, the classifiers with accuracy score above 80% were SVM, MNB, MLP, RF, LR, DT and K-NN. In addition, the study by Salloum et al (2022), analyzed articles on key research techniques and approaches in phishing detection to decide the most commonly used ML algorithms in phishing e-mail detection using Natural Language Processing (NLP) studies. The most common ML used in the studies includes SVM with 50 researches and the statistic for other classifiers is presented in Figure 8.

Based on the analysis of the ML techniques from the presented two approaches shown in Table 5 and Figure 8, this study evaluated SVM, MNB, MLP, RF, LR, DT, and K-NN to determine best performing algorithm in discovering malware-based phishing assaults.

3.5 Handling Dataset Imbalance

Most cybersecurity datasets are imbalanced with legitimate records overshadowing any phish labels. To deal with imbalanced datasets, various under and over sampling approaches such as Repeated Edited Nearest Neighbor, Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE) and ADASYN are used [27]. SMOTE's oversampling technique, which minimizes data loss, makes it a highly recommended choice for cybersecurity data mining. According to the study by Dewis & Viana, (2022), using an uneven dataset can significantly affect how well a

classifier performs. To mitigate this effect, SMOTE method has shown to be effective in achieving improved accuracy in a variety of fields, including bioinformatics and credit card fraud detection. To address the imbalance in the dataset in this study, SMOTE method, which is among the feature of WEKA tool, was used before classifier performance testing.

Figure 8: Summarized view of some ML-based techniques
Source: Salloum et al., (2022)

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Identified Features for Phishing E-mail Detection

Feature selection is a strategy for obtaining a subset from a larger feature group that meets particular feature selection criteria. According to the study by Gupta et al (2021) and Cai et al (2018), a well-chosen set of features can improve ML accurateness, streamline learning outcomes, and shorten learning time. In accordance with the e-mail dataset structure and the study by Aassal et al (2020), there are three basic feature classes that can be utilized in phishing e-mail uncovering. The three features are the header feature class, which comprises a timestamp, content format, recipient server, and other particulars, the body feature class, comprises two sub-classes (text features and URL classes), and the attachment class. These types of e-mail feature class are presented in figure 9 whereas each category at the lowest level is a subtree of finer feature categories.

Figure 9: E-mail feature taxonomy

The e-mail body is largely made up of semantic features, whereas the e-mail header is typically composed of routing features and a little number of semantic features (particularly for the subject) [31]. Based on all the analyzed articles in this study, the researcher examined the common features in all articles and obtained 31 features from both email

header and body used to detect phishing attacks. A hybrid feature selection approach comprising of 17 features obtained from both Pearson Feature Selection and URL-based Feature Selection was deployed and produced an enhanced classifier performance.

4.2 Evaluation for the effectiveness of ML detection techniques

The evaluation for the effectiveness of ML detection techniques involved simulation results obtained from the experiment with seven (7) major ML algorithms namely SVM (SMO), MNB, MLP, RF, LR, DT (REPTree) and K-NN which are commonly utilized in phishing e-mail classification and 10-fold cross-validation was preferred. Simulations were performed using datasets from different sources and WEKA tool was used to explore performance of the classifiers. In order to obtain an effective algorithm technique, the ML algorithms for uncovering malware-based phishing assaults were evaluated using six (6) performance metrics named confusion matrix, classification accuracy, recall, precision, F-Measure and Receiver Operating Characteristics (ROC).

4.2.1 English Phishing Dataset and Performance Measures

The English phishing dataset used in this study contain 14,651 instances whereby 6,234 are phishing and 8,417 are non-phishing e-mails. When SMOTE method was applied in WEKA tool to handle dataset imbalance, a total of 16,834 instances was obtained whereby phishing and non-phishing e-mails dataset are 8,417 each. This dataset was experimented by using the seven classifiers and the performance metrics of all classifiers are presented in Table 7 with RF the utmost with accuracy of 97.29%, precision 0.973, Recall of 0.973, F-Score of 0.973 and ROC area of 0.991 and it took 0.48 seconds to build the model. The closest classifier to RF is K-NN with accuracy of 97.27%.

Table 7: Performance of the classifiers in English phishing dataset

Classifier	Accuracy(%)	Precision	Recall	F-Measure	ROC	Time(Sec)
SVM	50.75	0.752	0.508	0.350	0.508	0.05
MNB	49.98	0.500	0.500	0.479	0.500	0
MLP	93.61	0.937	0.936	0.936	0.977	1.36
RF	97.29	0.973	0.973	0.973	0.991	0.48
LR	96.88	0.969	0.969	0.969	0.982	0.03
DT	97.24	0.973	0.972	0.972	0.990	0
K-NN	97.27	0.973	0.973	0.973	0.993	0

4.2.2 Swahili dataset and Performance Measures

The Swahili Phishing dataset mainly from Swahili language used in this study contain 1,687 instances whereby 78 are phishing and 1,609 are non-phishing e-mails. When SMOTE method was applied in WEKA tool to handle dataset imbalance for the 7 classifiers, a total of 3,217 instances was obtained whereby 1,608 are phishing and 1,609 are non-phishing e-mails. The percentages for the performance of all classifiers are shown in Table 8 with RF the highest with accuracy of 93.53%, precision 0.936, Recall of 0.935, F-Score of 0.935 and ROC area of 0.972 while it took 0.11 seconds to build the model. The closest classifier to RF was K-NN with accuracy of 93.50%.

Table 8: Performance of the classifiers in Swahili phishing dataset

Classifier	Accuracy(%)	Precision	Recall	F-Measure	ROC	Time (Sec)
SVM	51.54	0.535	0.515	0.436	0.515	0.02
MNB	49.95	0.499	0.500	0.450	0.499	0

MLP	55.02	0.566	0.550	0.521	0.591	0.27
RF	93.53	0.936	0.935	0.935	0.972	0.11
LR	54.03	0.573	0.540	0.481	0.850	0
DT	94.44	0.945	0.944	0.944	0.962	0
K-NN	93.50	0.935	0.935	0.935	0.970	0

4.2.3 COVID-19 related Dataset and Performance Measures

The COVID-19 related phishing dataset used in this study are collected from local mail systems and it contain 3,192 instances whereby 113 are phishing and 3,079 are non-phishing e-mails. When SMOTE method was applied to handle dataset imbalance for the 7 classifiers, a total of 6,158 instances was obtained whereby phishing and non-phishing e-mails dataset are 3,079 each. The percentages for the performance of all classifiers are shown in Table 9 with K-NN the highest with accuracy 86.52%, precision 0.867, Recall of 0.865, F-Score of 0.865 and ROC area of 0.895 while it took 0 seconds to build the model although the closest classifier to K-NN was RF with accuracy of 86.49%.

Table 9: Performance of the classifiers in COVID-19 phishing datasets

Classifier	Accuracy(%)	Precision	Recall	F-Measure	ROC	Time (Sec)
SVM	53.86	0.662	0.539	0.430	0.539	0.02
MNB	49.98	0.500	0.500	0.500	0.500	0
MLP	51.74	0.519	0.517	0.509	0.536	0.51
RF	86.49	0.867	0.865	0.865	0.909	0.4
LR	51.97	0.526	0.520	0.490	0.501	0.01
DT	83.18	0.832	0.832	0.832	0.891	0
K-NN	86.52	0.867	0.865	0.865	0.895	0

4.2.4 Combined Dataset and Performance Measures

The combined English Phishing, COVID-19 related content and Swahili Phishing dataset contains 19,403 instances, among them 6,424 instances are phishing dataset, and 12,797 are non-phishing dataset. When SMOTE method was applied to handle dataset imbalance for the 7 classifiers, a total of 25,958 instances was obtained whereby phishing and non-phishing e-mails dataset are 12,797 each. The performance outcomes for all classifiers are presented in Figure 10 with DT the highest with accuracy of 89.29%, precision 0.899, Recall of 0.893, F-Score of 0.893 and ROC area of 0.937 while it grabbed 0.01 seconds to build the model and the closest classifier to DT was RF with accuracy of 89.23%.

Figure 10: Average Classifiers Performance for Combined Primary Dataset

4.2.5 Classifiers Performance Measure from Secondary Datasets

As described in Table 3, a total of 11,056 secondary datasets that include 4,899 phishing and 6,157 non-phishing e-mails was gathered from different sources. The datasets are combined and experimented by using the 7 classifiers and when SMOTE method was applied, a total of 12,314 instances was obtained whereby phishing and non-phishing dataset are 6,157 each. The performance measures for all classifiers are shown in Table 11 and Figure 11 with RF highest with accuracy 97.52%, precision 0.975, Recall of 0.975, F-Score of 0.975 and ROC area of 0.997 while it took 0.6 seconds to build the model. The closest classifier to RF was K-NN with accuracy of 97.44% while the lowest was MNB with accuracy of 92.77%, although it took just 0 seconds to build the model.

Table 11: Performance of the Classifiers in Secondary Dataset

Classifier	Accuracy(%)	Precision	Recall	F-Measure	ROC	Time (Sec)
SVM	94.02	0.940	0.940	0.940	0.940	13.08
MNB	92.77	0.928	0.928	0.928	0.981	0
MLP	96.85	0.969	0.968	0.968	0.995	84.8
RF	97.52	0.975	0.975	0.975	0.997	0.6
LR	93.78	0.938	0.938	0.938	0.987	0.37
DT	95.55	0.956	0.955	0.955	0.986	0.14
K-NN	97.44	0.974	0.974	0.974	0.993	0

Figure 11: Average Classifiers Performance for Secondary Dataset

4.3 Enhancing the Accuracy of the best Performing Classifier

4.3.1 Enhancing the Accuracy by Feature Selection Using Pearson Correlation

The study by Rayan (2022), Zalavadia et al (2020), Al-Ajeli et al (2020), Baadel & Lu (2019), Nugraha et al (2022), Basnet et al (2012), Sinaga et al (2021) and Ozarkar & Patwardhan (2013) demonstrated that the feature selection procedure allows the subsequent machine learning classifier's performance to improve. Nugraha et al (2022) did an experiment in which he used a feature selection technique based on the Pearson correlation algorithm before performing ML modeling with common algorithms such as Naïve Bayes, Random Forest and Decision Tree. According to the study, adding the feature selection process based on the usage of Decision Tree and Random Forest algorithms produced a rise in accuracy of up to 94.60% and 95.50%, respectively [35]. Chunhui (2021) also demonstrated that duplicate features might increase processing time and reduce detection performance.

The correlation attribute evaluation results from the WEKA tool are shown in Figure 12 with correlation coefficient values. A correlation with a value of 0 is considered weak, a correlation with a value of 1 is considered strong and positive, and a correlation with a value of -1 is considered high but unfavourable. A dominating characteristic is one with a correlation coefficient of at least 0.1 and is used in the next stage of processing. There are 12 features with a correlation coefficient greater than the specified threshold of 0.1 (above the dotted red line). The performance is then tested using 10-fold cross-validation in terms of the obtained accuracy values, as presented in Table 12.

```
Attribute Evaluator (supervised, Class (nominal): 31 Result):
Correlation Ranking Filter
Ranked attributes:
0.650975    8 suspicious_subject
0.465975   14 hidden_link
0.367472    6 frequency_sensitive_word
0.311634   26 contain_javascript
0.261495    7 html_email
0.250491   13 suspicious_attachment
0.223279    9 suspicious_greetings
0.210206   16 message_size
0.164311   15 matched_domain
0.120496   24 nof_embedded_links_susp_symbol
0.117891   27 nof_embedded_links
0.117429   28 incorrect_use_ssl
-----
0.097243    1 IP_host
0.081766   25 nof_hyperlink_image
0.070873    3 nof_sensitive_words
0.070245   30 text_score
0.061127   18 nof_receivers
0.059177   29 suspicious_word_link
0.056274    2 nof_unique_words
0.040235   12 word_vector
0.039677    5 use_redirection
0.033762   20 nof_dots_url
0.030345    4 suspicious_symbol
0.026018   11 non_standard_port
0.012244   17 nof_attachment
0.011978   23 domain_information
0.011167   10 DKIM_signature
0.009949   22 nof_domains
0.008985   19 matched_senders
0.000411   21 suspicious_symbol_domain
```

Figure 11: E-mail Features with Correlation Coefficient

Figure 12: Filtered Correlation Coefficient greater than 0.1

Table 11: Comparison of Classifiers performance with/without Feature Selection

Classifier	Performance Without Feature Selection				Performance With Feature Selection			
	Accuracy (%)	Precision	Recall	F-Score	Accuracy (%)	Precision	Recall	F-Score
SVM	94.02	0.940	0.940	0.940	96.10	0.961	0.961	0.959
MNB	92.77	0.928	0.928	0.928	94.75	0.945	0.947	0.945
MLP	96.85	0.969	0.968	0.968	97.42	0.974	0.974	0.974
RF	97.52	0.975	0.975	0.975	98.03	0.983	0.980	0.980
LR	93.78	0.938	0.938	0.938	96.05	0.960	0.961	0.958
DT	95.55	0.956	0.955	0.955	96.54	0.965	0.965	0.964
K-NN	97.44	0.974	0.974	0.974	97.84	0.978	0.978	0.978

Figure 13: Comparison of Classifiers performance without and with Feature Selection

Figure 13 present the results of experiments performed with seven classifiers and two different modelling scenarios, namely modelling without feature selection and modelling with a feature selection process based on the correlation coefficient calculation. The leading classifier from the experiment without feature selection was RF algorithm with accuracy of 97.52%, and had an improved accuracy of 98.03% when the feature selection process was performed. This demonstrate that using feature selection improve classifier performance and ultimately mail phishing detection.

4.4 Enhancing the Accuracy of Classifier by URL Features Selection

The study by Khonji et al (2013), Sankhwar et al (2019), Mhaske-dhamdhare & Vanjale, (2019) and Yang et al (2019) demonstrated that by selecting important URL attributes, the performance of the resulting ML classifier can be differentiated between valid and malicious/phishing URLs. Sankhwar et al (2019), created an Enhanced Malicious URLs Detection (EMUD) model by combining URL-based features with classification approaches to achieve better classification and outcomes. The model focuses on the 14 relevant heuristics that distinguish between valid and malicious/phishing URLs, which were chosen after a thorough analysis of the literature and careful observation of phishing attack trends. The suggested model (EMUD) reached 93.01% accuracy with SVM which is higher than the previous model named Enhanced Probing Classification of Malicious URL (EPCMU) that achieved 84.58% in another experiment with the same classifier. Mhaske-dhamdhare & Vanjale, (2019) improved an anti-phishing system called PHISH SAFE-GUARD Phishing Detection (PSD-PD) using 4,327 dataset instances and 38

URL features. The researchers ran the dataset through Naïve Bayes, J48 and RF classifiers, and RF outperforming others with accuracy of 92%.

In order to provide an enhanced solution to combat against malicious phishing URLs, this study explored the performance of the classifiers by extracting URL-based features in the datasets. From 31 datasets used in the previous experiment, there were 11 URL related features extracted using WEKA tool based on information gain. When the classification performance is evaluated for the URL related features using 10-fold cross-validation in terms of the subsequent accuracy values, the classification performance showed less improvement in accuracy and other performance metrics used. The leading classifier from the experiment without URL-based features selection was Random Forest algorithm with accuracy of 97.52%, while the accuracy decreased to 90.26% when the URL-based features method was used. This demonstrate that using URL-based features alone is not enough for enhancing detection of phishing as some URL features can be irrelevant, non-dominant and legitimate in the e-mail dataset.

4.5 Enhancing the Accuracy of Classifier by Hybrid Features Selection

The study by Yang et al., (2019), Al-Ajeli et al., (2020), and Das Gupta et al., (2022) demonstrated that by using different hybrid feature selection method can increase the performance of the resultant machine learning classifier. Yang et al., (2019) presented 18 hybrid features, which included four e-mail header-based features, nine e-mail URL-based features, four e-mail script-based features, and one e-mail psychological feature, and achieved an overall true-positive rate of 99%, precision of 91.7%, and accuracy of 95.00%. Al-Ajeli et al., (2020) addressed the challenge of spam e-mail detection by establishing a detection methodology built on hybrid feature selection and SMO approaches, achieving an overall accuracy of 98.13%. Das Gupta et al., (2022) recommended a client-side only hybrid feature-based anti-phishing system that extracts features from URL-based features and hyperlink information. The experimental results demonstrated that the suggested phishing detection method was more effective, with 99.17% detection accuracy using the XG Boost technique.

To provide a more comprehensive background, recent studies and emerging trends in phishing detection and machine learning were considered. These include advancements in feature selection techniques, the application of deep learning models, and the integration of real-time adaptive mechanisms. This study explored the performance of the classifiers using hybrid features selection based on both dominant features selection from Pearson Correlation and URL-based features selection. The features selection by Pearson Correlation gives 12 features from correlation coefficient greater than 0.1 whereas URL-based features selection gives 11 features but six (6) features are in both categories thus making a total of 17 features as shown in Figure 14. When the classification performance is evaluated for the hybrid features selection using 10-fold cross-validation, the classifier performance improved and again RF was the leading classifier with accuracy of 99.28% as shown in Table 12 with comparison from the previous individual features selection method. Combining multiple machine learning models into hybrid or ensemble methods has been shown to improve detection performance. These methods leverage the strengths of individual models to provide more accurate and robust predictions.

Figure 14: Hybrid Features Selection by Correlation Ranking

4.6 Evaluation of Performance of the Classifiers

This study was achieved by different methodologies including conducting experiment by using the dataset that combined three datasets of different contents and from different sources. The produced dataset was tested in WEKA using seven classifiers: SVM (SMO), MLP, MNB, RF, DT, LR, and K-NN. However, before to merging that dataset, the researcher carried out an experiment by using individual category of dataset to determine the high performing classifier and the result for each category is summarized in Table 12.

Table 12: Leading Classifier Performance Summary

S/N	Type of Dataset	Experiment with Specific dataset	Leading Classifier	Accur acy %	2 nd Leading Classifier	Accur acy %
1	Primary dataset	English dataset	RF	97.29	KNN	97.27
		Swahili dataset	RF	93.53	K-NN	93.50
		COVID-19 dataset	K-NN	86.52	RF	86.49
		Combined dataset	DT	89.29	RF	89.23
2	Secondary dataset	Combined dataset from 3 sources	RF	97.52	K-NN	97.44
3	Category of Experiment	With Pearson Feature Selection	RF	98.03	K-NN	97.84
		With URL-based Feature Selection	RF	90.26	K-NN	90.08
		With Hybrid Features Selection	RF	99.28	K-NN	98.78

The result in all the experiments indicated that RF classifier was either the leading classifier in accuracy performance measure or the first runner up. It was also noted that the accuracy was higher in the experiment involving English dataset but slowly decreased from other datasets. Because of the small amount of phishing e-mails

in the Swahili dataset, the accuracy was significantly reduced, implying that e-mails in Swahili are slightly affected by phishing, but they can still be used to spread English phishing messages in e-mail communication.

Although the classifiers produced the lowest performance accuracy in COVID-19 dataset compared to other dataset, most of the classifiers performed well in detecting COVID-19 correlated phishing e-mails. This is consistent with the fact that, after discovering a significant increase in bad domain and phishing attempts during the COVID-19 pandemic phase, the existing anti-phishing software was improved to detect COVID-19 related malicious URL/phishing as per study by Salloum et al (2022) and Dewis & Viana (2022).

The result of the best performing classifier from all categories of datasets conforms to the fact that RF is a popular machine learning approach that involves very minimal data preparation or modeling yet typically gives a higher accuracy rate. RF generates numerous decision trees at random in order to categorize a new class, and all of the trees vote for that class and the most votes being chosen [44].

Figure 15: Comparison of Classifiers Performance with Hybrid Features Selection

Additionally, the classifiers performance accuracy was enhanced by using feature selection methods and URL-based features. When using feature selection methods, the dominant 12 features exceeding correlation coefficient of 0.1 threshold were extracted from 31 features in the dataset. The leading classifier from the experiment with feature selection using Pearson Correlation (PC) method was still RF algorithm with improved accuracy of 98.03% from 97.52% compared to without feature selection method. However, when using URL-based features method, 11 features were extracted and when the experiment was conducted using the same classifiers, the leading classifier was still RF although the accuracy decreased from 97.52% to 90.26% mostly due to small correlation coefficient of the features. This implies that URL-based features alone are not enough to improve classifier performance whereas Pearson Correlation feature selection improves classification performance in most of the classifiers and e-mail phishing detection. Nevertheless, when the research was conducted to determine the performance of the classifiers using hybrid features selection based on both Pearson Correlation features selection and URL features selection, the performance accuracies was observed to improve with the leading classifiers RF having accuracy of 99.28% compared to 98.03% when Pearson Correlation features selection was only used as seen in Figure 15.

4.7 Comparison to the Previous Research Works

This study tried to reduce the gaps observed from previous studies and the investigational results shows that the performance of the anticipated hybrid features selection approach that obtained accuracy of 99.28% is promising compared with previous methods. The other previous related works together with the used approaches are described in Table 13 for comparison whereas the researcher study had used more parameters and higher accuracy was observed except for one study that used Deep Learning technique.

Table 13: Comparison of Researcher Study with Previous Works

Study by	Study Title	Language	Classifiers	Approach Used	Performance Metric Used
Ozcan et al., (2021)	A hybrid DNN–LSTM model for identifying phishing URLs	English	NB, KNN, DT, RF, DNN and LSTM	A hybrid deep learning type of model based on DNN and LSTM	Accuracy 99.21%
Rafat et al., (2021)	Evading obscure communication from spam e-mails	English	Naïve Bayes, LSTM	Text pre-processing techniques	Accuracy 97.18%
Rastenis et al., (2021)	Multi-Language Spam/Phishing Classification by mail Body	English, Russian, Lithuania	NB, DT, RF, SVM, GBTrees	Automated translation for dataset augmentation	Accuracy 89.2%
A. El Aassal et al., (2020)	An In-Depth Benchmarking and Evaluation of Phishing Detection	English	RF, DT, LR, MNB, SVM, DL, KNN, Bag	A Novel taxonomy of features for phishing e-mails and URLs	Accuracy 99.95% For DL
Phomkeon a & Okamura, (2020)	Zero-day Malicious e-mail analysis and detection that uses DL Approach	English, Japanes, Chines, Lao	MLP, ANN	Deep learning with extraction of features from email header and body	Accuracy 92.8%
Yasin & Abuhasan, (2016)	An Intelligent Classification Model For Phishing E-mail Detection	English	J48, SVM, NB, RF and MLP	Concept of phishing terms weighting; text stemming	Accuracy 99.1%
Azeez & Ajayi, (2019)	Performance Evaluation of ML for detect Forged URLs	English	NB, DT, and LR	13 URLs Features extraction	Recall 0.83 Precision 1 F-Score 0.91
Dewis & Viana, (2022).	Phish Responder: A hybrid machine learning technique to recognize Phishing	English	LSTM and MLP	Combining natural language processing	Accuracy: LSTM 99%, MLP 94%
Sonowal, (2020)	Phishing e-mail revealing Based on Binary Search Feature Selection	English	BSFS, WFS and SFFS	Binary search feature selection	Accuracy 97.41% F-S - 97.78%
Aljohani et al., (2020)	Detection of phishing e-mails using data mining.	English	DT, LR, RF and ADA Boost	PILFER and Knowledge Discovery in DBs	Accuracy 98.07%
Nugraha et al., (2022)	Feature Selection for Improving classifiers Performance	English	NB, DT and RF	Feature Selection based on Pearson Correlation	Accuracy 95.50%
Researcher Study	Enhancing ML Detection Technique to Secure E-mail against Malware-based Phishing	English, Swahili	SVM, MNB, MLP, RF, LR, DT and K-NN.	Features Selection based on Pearson Correlation and URLs-based features	Accuracy 99.28% F-Score 0.993

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE RESEARCH

5.1 Conclusion

This paper evaluated ML detection approach for protecting e-mail communication from malware-based phishing attacks and the needed enhancement for the best performing algorithm. In particular, the seven popular ML algorithms namely SVM (SMO), MNB, MLP, RF, LR, DT (REPTree) and K-NN were evaluated based on the applied performance metrics and other parameters. The hybrid feature selection approach comprising of 17 features based on Pearson Feature Selection and URL-based Feature Selection were used. The findings showed that RF surpasses other classifiers with amazing accuracy of 99.28% and low false positive after augmentation by hybrid feature selection. The enhanced technique with the top performing classifier is therefore expected to provide accurate projecting model for reducing malware-based phishing attempts.

It was observed that, the two highest performing algorithms required significantly more processing time than the other methods, albeit the duration varies on the complexity of a dataset and the categorization. As a result, hybrid algorithms seems the greatest and most practicable method for detecting junk and phishing e-mails although it adds to the complexity of the implementation, which might be challenging for practical deployment. It is typically preferable to have adequate training samples with balanced allocations to acquire the highest detection performance. This study emphasizes the importance of evaluating the robustness of classification models, the requirement for several retraining sessions using novel attack types, and the need to modify feature sets to address evolving threats. Because attackers frequently vary their attack strategies in order to circumvent protection mechanisms, a dynamic style to phishing attack detection is required. Although retraining alone is insufficient to deal with phishing attacks, retraining current models with a more recent dataset somewhat enhances their ability to detect newer attacks.

5.2 Future Research Work

This research work has considered evaluation of standard ML algorithms used to detect malware-based phishing attempts in simple deployment scenarios with few evaluation parameters based on features due to software limitation and offline environment. For the future work, the study can be improved with more assessment parameters and focus on developing models that can adapt in real-time to new phishing tactics without the need for extensive retraining sessions. This could involve the use of online learning algorithms or reinforcement learning. It is also suggested to explore the integration of the proposed ML detection technique with other layers of security, such as behavioral analysis and network-level defenses, to provide a more comprehensive protection mechanism. Additionally, incremental feature performance valuation for each classifier is required to establish the features with a substantial influence on phishing discovery. This method will help the anti-malware strategy include additional distinguishing features in the classifier construction.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Baykara and Z. Z. Gürel, "Detection of phishing attacks," *6th Int. Symp. Digit. Forensic Secur. ISDFS 2018 - Proceeding*, vol. 2018-Janua, no. August, pp. 1–5, 2018, doi: 10.1109/ISDFS.2018.8355389.
- [2] Z. Alkhalil, C. Hewage, L. Nawaf, and I. Khan, "Phishing Attacks: A Recent Comprehensive Study and a New Anatomy," *Front. Comput. Sci.*, vol. 3, no. March, pp. 1–23, 2021, doi: 10.3389/fcomp.2021.563060.
- [3] A. Basit, M. Zafar, X. Liu, A. R. Javed, Z. Jalil, and K. Kifayat, "A comprehensive survey of AI-enabled phishing attacks detection techniques," *Telecommun. Syst.*, vol. 76, no. 1, pp. 139–154, 2021, doi: 10.1007/s11235-020-00733-2.

- [4] A. Ozcan, C. Catal, E. Donmez, and B. Senturk, "A hybrid DNN–LSTM model for detecting phishing URLs," *Neural Comput. Appl.*, vol. 0123456789, 2021, doi: 10.1007/s00521-021-06401-z.
- [5] FBI's IC3, "2020 Internet Crime Report," *Fed. Bur. Investig. - Internet Crime Complain. Cent.*, pp. 1–28, 2020, [Online]. Available: https://www.ic3.gov/Media/PDF/AnnualReport/2020_IC3Report.pdf.
- [6] S. Rameem Zahra, M. Ahsan Chishti, A. Iqbal Baba, and F. Wu, "Detecting Covid-19 Chaos Driven Phishing/Malicious URL Attacks by a Fuzzy Logic and Data Mining based Intelligence System," *Egypt. Informatics J.*, no. xxxx, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.eij.2021.12.003.
- [7] Meenu and S. godara, "Phishing Detection using Machine Learning Techniques," *Int. J. Eng. Adv. Technol.*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 3820–3829, 2019, doi: 10.35940/ijeat.b4095.129219.
- [8] D. Gibert, C. Mateu, and J. Planes, "The rise of machine learning for detection and classification of malware: Research developments, trends and challenges," *J. Netw. Comput. Appl.*, vol. 153, no. November 2019, p. 102526, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.jnca.2019.102526.
- [9] J. Rashid, T. Mahmood, M. W. Nisar, and T. Nazir, "Phishing Detection Using Machine Learning Technique," *Proc. - 2020 1st Int. Conf. Smart Syst. Emerg. Technol. SMART-TECH 2020*, pp. 43–46, 2020, doi: 10.1109/SMART-TECH49988.2020.00026.
- [10] J. Gori Mohamed and J. Visumathi, "A predictive model of machine learning against phishing attacks and effective defense mechanisms," *Mater. Today Proc.*, no. xxxx, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.matpr.2020.09.612.
- [11] B. B. Gupta, K. Yadav, I. Razzak, K. Psannis, A. Castiglione, and X. Chang, "A novel approach for phishing URLs detection using lexical based machine learning in a real-time environment," *Comput. Commun.*, vol. 175, no. November 2020, pp. 47–57, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.comcom.2021.04.023.
- [12] M. V. Madhavan, S. Pande, P. Umekar, T. Mahore, and D. Kalyankar, "Comparative analysis of detection of email spam with the aid of machine learning approaches," *IOP Conf. Ser. Mater. Sci. Eng.*, vol. 1022, no. 1, 2021, doi: 10.1088/1757-899X/1022/1/012113.
- [13] M. Aldwairi, M. Hasan, and Z. Balbahaith, "Detection of drive-by download attacks using machine learning approach," *Int. J. Inf. Secur. Priv.*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 16–28, 2017, doi: 10.4018/IJISP.2017100102.
- [14] M. Tubyte and A. Paulauskaite-Taraseviciene, "Research on phishing email detection based on URL parameters using machine learning algorithms," *CEUR Workshop Proc.*, vol. 2915, pp. 18–26, 2021.
- [15] M. Alshira'h and M. Al-Fawa'reh, "Detecting phishing urls using machine learning lexical feature-based analysis," *Int. J. Adv. Trends Comput. Sci. Eng.*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 5828–5837, 2020, doi: 10.30534/ijatcse/2020/242942020.
- [16] Abdul Abiodun, Orunsolu; A.S, K. Sodiya; S.O, and O. G. M. B, "Performance Assessment of some Phishing predictive models based on Minimal Feature corpus," *J. Digit. Forensics, Secur. Law*, vol. 16, no. 5, 2021.
- [17] S. C. Et. al., "A Survey on Machine Learning Approach to Detect Malware," *Turkish J. Comput. Math. Educ.*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 2309–2314, 2021, doi: 10.17762/turcomat.v12i2.1961.
- [18] U. De Barcelona and V. Carvalho, "EMAIL FRAUD CLASSIFIER USING MACHINE LEARNING," 2020.
- [19] A. Malero, "Applying feature transformation using Relative Frequency with Power Transformation and Lemmatization in automatic Spam Filtering," vol. 2, no. 10, pp. 21–27, 2014.
- [20] J. Rastenis, S. Ramanauskaitė, I. Suzdalev, K. Tunaitytė, J. Janulevičius, and A. Čenys, "Multi-language spam/phishing classification by email body text: Toward automated security incident investigation," *Electron.*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 1–10, 2021, doi: 10.3390/electronics10060668.
- [21] S. Phomkeona and K. Okamura, "Zero-day malicious email investigation and detection using features with deep-learning approach," *J. Inf. Process.*, vol. 28, pp. 222–229, 2020, doi: 10.2197/ipsjip.28.222.
- [22] R. Alamri and B. Alharbi, "Explainable Student Performance Prediction Models: A Systematic Review," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 33132–33143, 2021, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3061368.
- [23] I. Property *et al.*, "RFC 2822 and MIME to Email Object Conversion Algorithm," pp. 1–125, 2021.
- [24] A. Rayan, "Analysis of e-Mail Spam Detection Using a Novel Machine Learning-Based Hybrid Bagging Technique," vol. 2022, 2022.
- [25] N. M. Masanja and H. Mkumbo, "The Application of Open Source Artificial Intelligence as an Approach to Frugal Innovation in Tanzania," *Int. J. Res. Innov. Appl. Sci. /*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 2454–6194, 2020.
- [26] R. Jidagam and N. Rizk, "Evaluation of Predictive Data Mining Algorithms in Student Academic Performance," *INTED2016 Proc.*, vol. 1, no. March, pp. 6314–6324, 2016, doi: 10.21125/inted.2016.0487.
- [27] A. El Aassal, S. Baki, A. Das, and R. M. Verma, "An In-Depth Benchmarking and Evaluation of Phishing

- Detection Research for Security Needs,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 22170–22192, 2020, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2969780.
- [28] M. Dewis and T. Viana, “Phish Responder: A Hybrid Machine Learning Approach to Detect Phishing and Spam Emails,” *Appl. Syst. Innov.*, vol. 5, no. 4, 2022, doi: 10.3390/asi5040073.
- [29] S. Salloum, T. Gaber, S. Vadera, and K. Shaalan, “A Systematic Literature Review on Phishing Email Detection Using Natural Language Processing Techniques,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 65703–65727, 2022, doi: 10.1109/access.2022.3183083.
- [30] A. E. L. Aassal, S. Baki, A. Das, and R. M. Verma, “An In-Depth Benchmarking and Evaluation of Phishing Detection Research for Security Needs,” vol. 8, 2020.
- [31] Y. Fang, C. Zhang, C. Huang, L. Liu, and Y. U. E. Yang, “Phishing Email Detection Using Improved RCNN Model With Multilevel Vectors and Attention Mechanism,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 56329–56340, 2019, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2913705.
- [32] F. Zalavadia, S. Pandey, P. Pachpande, and A. Nevrekar, “Detecting Phishing Attacks Using Natural Language Processing and Deep Learning models,” vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 579–590, 2020.
- [33] A. Al-Ajeli, R. Alubady, and E. S. Al-Shamery, “Improving spam email detection using hybrid feature selection and sequential minimal optimisation,” *Indones. J. Electr. Eng. Comput. Sci.*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 535–542, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v19.i1.pp535-542.
- [34] S. Baadel and J. Lu, “Data Analytics: Intelligent Anti-Phishing Techniques Based on Machine Learning,” *J. Inf. Knowl. Manag.*, vol. 18, no. 1, 2019, doi: 10.1142/S0219649219500059.
- [35] A. F. Nugraha, D. A. Tama, D. A. Istiqomah, S. T. A. Ramadhani, B. N. Kusuma, and V. A. Windarni, “Feature Selection Technique for improving classification performance in the web-phishing detection process,” *Conf. Ser.*, vol. 4, no. January, pp. 25–31, 2022, doi: 10.34306/conferenceseries.v4i1.667.
- [36] R. B. Basnet, A. H. Sung, and Q. Liu, “Feature selection for improved phishing detection,” *Lect. Notes Comput. Sci. (including Subser. Lect. Notes Artif. Intell. Lect. Notes Bioinformatics)*, vol. 7345 LNAI, pp. 252–261, 2012, doi: 10.1007/978-3-642-31087-4_27.
- [37] A. S. Sinaga, M. H. Munandar, and A. S. Sitio, “Machine learning algorithm to identifies fraud emails with feature selection,” *IOP Conf. Ser. Mater. Sci. Eng.*, vol. 1088, no. 1, p. 012011, 2021, doi: 10.1088/1757-899x/1088/1/012011.
- [38] P. Ozarkar and M. Patwardhan, “Efficient Spam Classification by Appropriate Feature Selection,” *Glob. J. Comput. Sci. Technol. Softw. Data Eng.*, vol. 13, no. 5, pp. 1–11, 2013.
- [39] M. Khonji, Y. Iraqi, A. Jones, P. O. Box, P. O. Box, and A. Dhahi, “Enhancing Phishing E-Mail Classifiers : A Lexical URL Analysis Approach,” vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 236–245, 2013.
- [40] S. Sankhwar, D. Pandey, and R. A. Khan, “EAI Endorsed Transactions on Scalable Information System s Email Phishing : An Enhanced Classification Model to Detect Malicious URLs.”
- [41] V. Mhaske-dhamdhare and S. Vanjale, “PHISH SAFE GURAD-Phishing Detection: Enhance Anti-Phishing System Using Machine Learning Algorithm,” no. 4, pp. 1668–1671, 2019.
- [42] Z. Yang, C. Qiao, W. Kan, and J. Qiu, “Phishing Email Detection Based on Hybrid Features,” *IOP Conf. Ser. Earth Environ. Sci.*, vol. 252, no. 4, 2019, doi: 10.1088/1755-1315/252/4/042051.
- [43] S. Das Gupta, K. T. Shahriar, H. Alqahtani, D. Alsalman, and I. H. Sarker, “Modeling Hybrid Feature-Based Phishing Websites Detection Using Machine Learning Techniques,” *Ann. Data Sci.*, 2022, doi: 10.1007/s40745-022-00379-8.
- [44] G. Sonowal, “Phishing Email Detection Based on Binary Search Feature Selection,” *SN Comput. Sci.*, vol. 1, no. 4, pp. 1–14, 2020, doi: 10.1007/s42979-020-00194-z.
- [45] K. F. Rafat, Q. Xin, A. R. Javed, Z. Jalil, and R. Zeeshan, “Evading obscure communication from spam emails,” vol. 19, no. November, pp. 1926–1943, 2021.
- [46] A. Yasin and A. Abuhasan, “An Intelligent Classification Model for Phishing Email Detection,” *Int. J. Netw. Secur. Its Appl.*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 55–72, 2016, doi: 10.5121/ijnsa.2016.8405.
- [47] N. A. Azeez and A. A. Ajayi, “Performance evaluation of machine learning techniques for identifying forged and phony uniform resource locators (URLs),” *Niger. J. Technol. Dev.*, vol. 16, no. 4, pp. 155–169, 2019, doi: 10.4314/NJTD.V16I4.2.
- [48] S. Aljohani, Abeerabushikha, S. Altuwarqui, and A. Subasi, “Detection of phishing website using data mining techniques,” *J. Adv. Res. Dyn. Control Syst.*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 413–421, 2020, doi: 10.5373/JARDCS/V12I2/S20201059.